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Research Article

**STUDY OF STONE FORMATION ASSOCIATED URINARY
TRACT INFLAMMATION AND METABOLIC DISORDERS**¹Sher Muhammad Khan, ²Muhammad Waqas, ³Muhammad Ahmed Khan¹Nishtar Medical University, Multan.²King Edward Medical University, Lahore.³The University Of Lahore, Lahore.**Article Received:** October 2020**Accepted:** November 2020**Published:** December 2020**Abstract:**

Objective: The main objective was to establish the association between the development of stones in metabolic diseases and the urinary tract inflammation caused by them.

Place and duration of study: This study was performed in Nishtar Hospital Multan's urology department over nine months from March 2020 to November 2020.

Materials and methods: This research involved a total of 100 patients. Both genders were randomly picked. The urine sample, which was then sent to a reputable laboratory to examine specific gravity, pH, uric acid, creatinine, calcium oxalate, phosphate, magnesium, and citrate, was collected by each patient for 24 hours. Each patient's thorough history was taken. To collect the samples, plastic boxes that were inert were used and then stored at 2-8 oC. Samples of blood were also sent to search for creatinine, phosphate, urea, uric acid, and calcium levels.

Results: Of the 100 selected patients, 65 were female, and 35 were male, with a mean age of 38 years. The lumbar pain complaint accompanied by burning micturition and hematuria was presented by 79 per cent of patients. Ninety-four per cent of the patients were diagnosed with ureteric renal stones. In 38 per cent of the cases, the real stone formation was seen, while 62 per cent of patients suffered from it for the first time. After extensive chemical analysis, calcium oxalate was seen in 82.5 per cent of the cases.

Conclusion: Results of the study showed that those patients who have metabolic abnormalities, have a high incidence of stone formation and stone formation is also high in patients who have hyperoxaluria, hypocitraturia, are the common abnormalities seen.

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INTRODUCTION:

the disease or condition by which most of the population is affected is urolithiasis. Real stones are mostly seen in the twenties and thirties of life, and these are seen in approximately 2% of the population. There are many types of urinary stones, and these are grouped according to their chemical composition. Many factors cause urolithiasis, including gender, age, heredity, climate, and metabolic abnormalities. These factors cannot be modified except metabolic abnormalities that can be modified to decrease the risk of stone formation. Indwelling catheters are used to reduce the symptoms of urinary retention and incontinence. The number of Foley catheters sold per annum is 100 million, of these 25 million are sold in the US. Catheters that are used in routine, Foley's catheter is the most common among them. The catheter has a latex tube or sterile tube. The tube has an inflatable balloon at its one end. This balloon prevents the displacement of the catheter. Prolonged use of catheters can lead to urinary tract infections. Infections caused by these catheters cause severe dysfunction and have a high incidence.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This research involved a total of 100 patients. Both genders were randomly picked. The urine sample, which was then sent to a reputable laboratory to examine specific gravity, pH, uric acid, creatinine, calcium oxalate, phosphate, magnesium, and citrate, was collected by each patient for 24 hours. Each patient's thorough history was taken. To collect the samples, plastic boxes that were inert were used and then stored at 2-8 °C. Samples of blood were also sent to search for creatinine, phosphate, urea, uric acid, and calcium levels.

RESULTS:

A total of 100 patients were picked, from these, 35 patients were male, and 65 were female patients, and 38 years were mean age. Of these, 79% patients were presented with a history of low back pain, followed by hematuria and micturition. The diagnosis of 94% of patients was real stone ureteric. About 62% of patients were suffered from renal stones for the first time, while 38% of patients have recurrent stone formation. Detailed chemical analysis of 82% of patients showed calcium oxalate stones.

DISCUSSION:

urinary stones of various types are the third most common disease of the urinary system. In Pakistan, the formation of stones in the urinary system is the most common disease. The incidence in different regions of the same country and among different countries is

seen. In the 20th century, the incidence of urinary stone formation had increased by about 15% of the population. Males are more commonly affected as compared to females. This result is linked to past research. At any stage of life, stone-forming may occur. Seventy-nine per cent of the patients had lumbar pain, according to our report. Research by Elfadil GA *et al.* found that 67% of patients had lumbar pain. In 64 per cent of our patients, the genetic factor plays an essential role in stone formation, and genetic predisposition was identified, confirmed by the research performed by Majalan NN *et al.* and Kiran M *et al.*, in which 53.1 per cent and 67 per cent of patients had a family history of stone formation. In 38 per cent of our patients, the persistent urinary stone formation was found, consisting primarily of calcium oxalate, which is correlated with the Elfadil GA *et al.* study. 90.5 per cent of our patients had metabolic aberrations, whereas there was only 9.5 per cent of patients with no abnormality. This research coincides with that performed by Amaro *et al.*, in which 62.2 per cent of patients had related metabolic disorders, but no repeated stone formation of calcium oxalate was seen. Therefore, it can be concluded that in cases with several metabolic aberrations, calcium oxalate stone formation is much more common. 71.3 per cent of patients in the Kiran M *et al.* study had numerous metabolic disorders, and our study showed a percentage of 71.3 per cent.

CONCLUSION:

Results of the study showed that those patients who have metabolic abnormalities, have a high incidence of stone formation and stone formation is also high in patients who have hyperoxaluria, hypocitraturia, are the common abnormalities seen.

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